

HISTORY OF DIAMONDS

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Abstract:

In order to know about a diamond completely, it is necessary to know how diamond is formed and its evolution. The history of all objects in the world is very important. By knowing the historical information of an object, we can understand much basic information about that object.

Key Words: History of Diamond, Clarity, Cut, Colour, Mining, Possession, Expensive Diamond

Introduction:

Diamond has the history of about more than 2000 years. In this article formation of diamonds, mining process, importance of cutting a raw diamond, polishing procedures, rarity of the gemstone, preciousness of the diamond, appearance of the diamond in an ornament, expensive diamonds in the world, details of highest sold diamond in auction are all detailly analyzed.

History of Diamonds:

Etymology of diamond explains that the name is originated from an ancient greek word called "Adamas". The word "Adamas" in ancient Greek means indestructible - cannot be easily damaged or destroyed, invincible - too strong or powerful to be defeated, unconquerable - impossible to overcome or defeat. Diamond's name is defined by its properties. Related names of diamond's are Deimanté, Diamanda, Dymond, diamanto.

The diamond was found below 100 miles from the earth surface and they took 1 to 3 billion years to form. It forms under the earth because of extreme heat and pressure. In another perspective a diamond on a jewel is five times older than a Dinosaur. It is ejected violently upward until it arrives at or near the earth's surface. It is forced from its hiding place by nature or by man. Diamonds are really hard to get because of these reasons. From ancient period to modern age there is always have the demand for diamond because of its rarity, design, value and its precious look.

Diamonds were first discovered and mined in India around 2500 years ago in the Golconda region between the Godavari and Krishna rivers. Diamonds were prized as divine objects by Indian rulers. In Sanskrit diamond was named as vajra, thunderbolt, Indrayudha. These names are directly related to the God Indira. Vajrayutham is the weapon of God Indira and he is also referred as God of lightning. In Sanskrit manuscripts the name diamond was mentioned by a minister in the northern Indian dynasty which was dated in 3rd century i.e. 320-296 BCE.

By 4th century diamond became a valuable material in India and most of the people in India had the awareness about the importance and the usage of the diamond in that ancient period itself.

But it was only in 13th century the European countries were developing their knowledge towards diamonds. After the development of diamond faceting, the diamond market became larger and more prominent by 16th century.

Louis IX who ruled France in 13th century established a law that "Diamonds are only king's property" because of its incomparable values and its rarity. In the early period diamond jewelry were only made for the king's dynasty later the jewelry was made to the royal families. Initially only men were allowed to wear diamonds. After sometime royal women in the European aristocracy were allowed to wear and after that period diamond jewelry were made to the wealthiest business class people in Europe.

By the middle of 13th century diamond cutting was primarily erected in Venice and only in the 14th century it was extended to Paris.

The turning point in the history of diamond was took place when the Portuguese navigator Vasco da Gama discovered sea route to India because Indians are the first people to know about diamonds and they mastered the usage of diamonds before other countries know about the name of it.

By the time of 17th century jewelries were made by small diamond stones and by the time of 18th century many jewelries are made with larger diamond stones. At its early stage cutting and polishing had yet to be mastered, so diamonds retained their natural outer skin which means it remained unrefined.

In the first century AD, Roman naturalists said "Diamond is the most valuable, not only of precious stones, but of all things in the world".

A diamond has to go through a lot of process before it reaches the jewelry shop. Diamonds was first gathered in the river side of India and the people of India had developed the creativity towards diamond.

At earlier stage diamonds were only the possessions of the Rulers of the country and after some time slowly diamond make its own way of business expansion through its own values.

By the time of 14th century diamond became the fashionable accessories for European's also. In the early 17th century supply of diamonds to the market has begun to decline in India mean while Brazil emerged as a new and an important source of diamond supply.

At early-stage Brazil had some struggles in diamond mining and its transportation but once it reached its full potential, Brazil remained in the diamond market as a domination source of supply for nearly two decades.

In late 17th century French revolution took place which results in the decline of diamond purchase due to economic deficit. But that was not an end. Diamond demand the broadening of the market and hence it reaches United states and Western Europe. Due to that demand the explorer's unearthed the South African diamond deposits in the late 18th century. That period created a revolution in the diamond market. The modern diamond market was really begins on the African continent in the 19th century.

In the beginning stage diamonds were remained natural and unpolished which means they remained as raw diamonds only. Slowly the appearance of the diamond stones was enhanced by its unique cutting methods and polishing which made them more valuable than other stones. Diamond is known for its clarity and colour. Rather than other stones diamonds are always precious. After the introduction of efficient mining techniques, the price of diamond became reasonable and the consumption of diamond accessories to the people became easier. Because of the modern techniques the appearance of the finished diamonds became more perfect and elegant.

French Dynasty sold the diamond crown jewel in 1887 had changed the people's enumeration towards diamond. Diamond jewels were also known for its incomparable and incomputable designs of its own. Based on these criteria's diamond created a strong market and the demand that was created has still lasting. Nowadays diamonds are mined in about 25 countries. The production of diamond was increased enormously.

In 1870's the annual production of raw diamond was around 1 million carats. By 1920's the production was increased up to 3 million carats. But it was tremendously developed to 50 million carats within fifty years and reached 100 million carats of annual production by the year 1990.

In 1970's world's most important rough diamond producers were South Africa, democratic republic of Congo and Russia. Around 1985 the diamond mining was expanded in Australia and Northern Canada. Diamond knowledge has grown steadily with research by chemists, physicists, geologists, mineralogists and oceanographers. In the past 50 years of research, scientists have learned a lot about diamond formation and how they are transported to the earth's surface. This made easier in the prediction of the location for new diamond mining's.

The natural beauty of the diamond attracts many cultures and continents. Early Hindus believed that the diamonds were created when bolts of lightning stuck rocks. Greeks believed that the creation was made by the splinters of stars that had fallen to Earth. Meanwhile Roman philosophers considered them as tears of God. Plato even believed that diamonds were living beings that embodied celestial spirits.

Lots of myths are surrounded by diamonds. In Hindu mythology people believed that diamonds have some magical properties to protect the people against any poisonous things, evil spirits and fire. Romans believed that wearing a diamond in the battle war gave strength and courage in the battle.

From 10th century onwards, the western countries began to develop the economic access to diamonds through the trade routes and soon diamonds became the status symbol. It was during this period diamond ring became a symbol of marriage in western countries.

There is a famous quote which was recorded in a priest manual named Guillaume During in the year 1286 was "The diamond is unbreakable and love unquenchable and longer the death, so its suits to be wear in the ring finger, the vein of which comes directly from the heart". The idea of wearing a diamond ring as a symbol of engagement continues for the following centuries.

Diamond cutting technique was first discovered in the latter half of the 14th century in Italy results in the introduction of new cuts including faceted and fancy cuts.

Diamond became the symbol of power in European court also. King Francis I who ruled France introduced the first crown jewel which contain fourteen diamonds.

Importance of Diamond Cut:

When diamonds are mined from the Earth, the appearance was rough and unrefined. There is a lot of processing methods to make a rough diamond into a diamond we know. Diamond cutting is not an easy job that everybody can do. It requires efficiency and knowledge for the procedures and also it needs tools, equipment and techniques. There are two basic elements in the technique in which one was its shape and other related to the specific quality of cut within the shape. The uniqueness and the price will depend upon the quality of the cut in the diamonds.

The process of diamond cutting includes many steps.

- Planning
- Cleaving or sawing
- Bruiting
- Polishing
- Final inspection

In detail planning means choosing a right place for diamond mining. Cleaving is the process which separates the rough diamond into separate pieces. Sawing mean cutting the separate pieces with laser cutting technique to make it as a separate gem. Bruiting is a process where two diamonds are set in to a spinning axis pans turning in opposite directions which results in grinding to make each diamond in to a round shape.

Polishing is the final process to make the diamond's appearance as a brilliant sparkle. Final inspection of diamond involves the cleaning of diamond with some acids and the quality checking to reach the standard of diamond manufacturers.

Types of Diamond Cuts:

Brilliant cut, step cut, mixed cut, fancy cut and cut grading. Classic round cut is referred as brilliant cut. Among all these types of cutting brilliant cut diamond is considered as the most popular and most expensive diamonds in the world.

Common types of cuts and shapes

- Princess Cut Diamond
- Emerald Cut Diamond
- Cushion Cut Diamond
- Marquise Cut Diamond
- Pear Cut Diamond
- Rose Cut Diamond
- Radiant Cut Diamond
- Heart Cut Diamond
- Old Mine Cut Diamond
- Oval Cut Diamond
- Round Cut Diamond
- Phoenix Cut Diamond

In these common types of cuts and shape Phoenix cut diamond has the highest facets of about 89. Like any other precious gemstones, the price of a diamond depends on certain factors relating to its weight and clarity. These two things play major role among the other things.

The value of a diamond and the price rating is decided by the combinations of four Cs.

- Carat
- Cut
- Colour
- Clarity

Carat is the weight of a diamond 1 carat = 0.2 grams

Cut is the shape of the diamond. The highest grade is termed as Ideal or Excellent

Colour ranges from brilliant white to shades of yellow, pink, blue, red and green. Colourless diamonds are the rarest and are the most expensive. Although some of the world's most expensive diamonds are especially blue and pink. These diamonds created world record in their auction because they were very rare pieces and never have been sold to the common people.

Clarity is a measure of the purity and rarity of the stone, graded by the visibility of these characteristics under 10 power magnification.

Most Expensive Diamonds:

There are 15 most expensive diamonds in the world

- Koh-I-Noor
- The Cullinan
- The Hope
- De Beers Centenary
- CTF Pink Star diamond
- Williamson Pink star
- Oppenheimer blue diamond
- De Beers Blue
- Blue moon of Josephine
- Graff Pink
- Bleu Royal
- The Princie Diamond
- The Orange
- The Eternal Pink
- The Zoe Diamond
- Koh-I-Noor

Koh-I-Noor means "Mountain of light" and the gem is considered as the world's most famous, most expensive, most precious and priceless diamond. The original weight of Koh-I-Noor diamond was 793 carats. But it has been cut and polished over centuries so now the present Koh-I-Noor diamond weighs only 105.6 carats only.

The Koh-I-Noor diamond was mined in the Golconda region which was located in India. Initially the diamond was in the Kakatiya Dynasty. Later it comes to Mughal Dynasty. After defeating the Mughal emperor by Shah of Persia he took the diamond along with the peacock throne in which it was encrusted to his country. In 1813 Maharaja Ranjith Singh possessed the diamond. But in 19th century British conquered India and it became the possession of British Royal Family. The Koh-I-Noor diamond was mounted in the crown which was a belonging of Late Queen Elizabeth, the Queen mother. The public were last seen the precious diamond when the crown was placed on the top of the coffin of Queen Elizabeth in the year 2002.

The Cullinan:

The Cullinan diamond was mined in south Africa in 1905. The original weight was about 3,106 carats which was the largest rough diamond in the history. But in nowadays it is a collection of about 105 pieces of different cuts and weights.

The Cullinan, one of the most magnificent diamonds was named after Thomas Cullinan, the chairman of the mine. The total worth of the gems stone is about 400 million USD in the current market.

Among 105 pieces nine pieces are larger in their sizes and the total weight is approximately of about 1,055 carats in which the biggest piece is known as Cullinan I and the weight of this diamond is about 530.20 carats. It has the record of largest clear-cut diamond in the world. The Cullinan I is mounted on the spectra of British Monarch, King Charles III.

The Cullinan II weighing 317.40 carats is the belongings of Imperial State Crown. Cullinan III, IV, and V are mounted in Queen Elizabeth II's pendent. And the remaining four are also the part of Queen's personal jewelry.

The Hope:

A diamond weighing 112 carat which was purchased by a French traveler called Jean Baptise Tavernier who was known as Hope. This diamond was also found in Golconda mine where Koh-I-Noor diamond was found. It is a beautiful violet colour gem stone and he recorded this in his diary. He sold it to the King Louis XIV. After long period the diamond is came to be recognized as the "Blue Diamond of the Crown". But the diamond was stolen in 1792 and it was found in London in the year 1812. After changing in several hands, the diamond ended up in Smithsonian Institution in the year 1958.

The Hope diamond has remained in this Institution's collection and has been displayed for the public only for four times. The weight of the diamond is 45 carats and its estimated worth is about 200 to 350 million USD.

De Beers Centenary:

De Beers centenary diamond was discovered in the premier mine in South Africa in 1986. but the existence of the diamond was announced two years later at the 100th anniversary of De Beers in Kimberly. This is the reason behind the name of this diamond.

This diamond weights about 599 carats and it has the record that one of the world's largest top-colour diamonds. Later the diamond was cut down into a heart-shaped gem stone of about 273.85 carats with 247 perfectly aligned facets.

The GIA certified the diamond's colour as D -the highest rating for colourless diamonds. The diamond is internally and externally flawless in clarity at the time of 1991

It was the largest known colourless modern cut diamond and it was insured for 100 million USD before it was displayed in the year 1991. But now the current location of the diamond is unknown and it remains as a mystery.

CTF Pink Star Diamond:

CTF Pink Star Diamond is the world's largest vivid pink diamond. The exact location of the diamond is unknown. It was mined in Africa by De Beers in 1999.

The original weight of the stone is about 132.5 carats. After some years experts cut and polished it into a 59.60 carat diamond. It was first displayed in Monaco in 2003 that time it was known as Steinmetz Pink Diamond.

In April 2017 this diamond was sold for 71.2 million USD in an auction to a jewelry company Chow Tai Fook. The owner of the company is a billionaire Henry Cheng renamed the diamond as CTF Pink Star Diamond.

This is the most expensive diamond that was ever sold in the auction.

Williamson Pink Star:

In Hong Kong Williamson Pink Star diamond was sold in an auction which was held in October 7, 2022 for 57.7 million USD. The diamond weight was about 11.15 carats it was a cushion-cut diamond thus became the second most valuable jewel or gem stone ever sold in auction.

The diamond was found in the Williamson Mine in Tanzania after which is named. Williamson Pink Star was owned by the late Queen Elizabeth II who was passed away on 8 September 2022.

Oppenheimer Blue Diamond:

Before the CTF Pink star, the Oppenheimer Blue was the costliest diamond to have been sold at an auction for 57.5 million USD at Christie's Geneva Magnificent Jewels sale in 2016.

This was an 14.62 carat diamond and graded as fancy vivid blue diamond and named after its owner Sri Philip Oppenheimer, one of the dominant power in De Beers Mining company. It is an extremely rare diamond because only 10 percent of all blue diamonds are larger than a carat. This is an Emerald-cut Diamond and has the clarity grade of VVS1.

De Beers Blue:

This diamond is weighing about 15.10 carat and it is the largest vivid blue diamond ever to appear at auction. Only five blue diamonds of over 10 carats have previously been sold at auctions.

This diamond was cut from a rough stone discovered in South Africa's historic Cullinan mine in April 2021. GIA graded this diamond as the largest internally flawless step cut vivid blue diamond.

Blue Moon of Josephine:

In November 2015, the vivid blue diamond sold for 48.4 million USD at an auction in Hong Kong. At the time, 12.03 carat diamond was the costliest ever to have been sold at an auction.

The blue moon diamond was bought by Hong Kong billionaire Joseph Lau for his daughter and he renamed it as Blue moon of Josephine.

In 2014 the diamond was discovered in the Cullinan mine by Petra Diamonds in south Africa weighing 29.6 carats. They sold the diamond to Coral International.

Graff Pink:

The Graff Pink diamond was last sold in 2010 in an auction for 46.2 million USD. It gets its name from its current owner - Laurence Graff of Graff Diamonds. The diamond's weight is about 24.78 carat. It is a Fancy Pink Emerald cut diamond was not seen on the market for 60 years before the sale. After enhancing the look Graff Pink is now 23.88 carat internally flawless fancy vivid pink diamond. Because of its colour and size it is considered as a rare diamond.

Bleu Royal:

Christies in Geneva sold the Bleu Royal diamond in November 2023 for 43.8 million USD weighing of 17.6 carats. Christie's jewelry department head Max Fawcett said that the diamond was unique because of its deep rich blue colour and its unmodified pear brilliant shape.

The Princie Diamond:

The Princie Diamond is one of the world's best known pink diamonds and it is one of the most expensive diamonds too. In the year 2013 the diamond was sold for 39.3 million USD in New York city 's Christie's auction.

This diamond was discovered in Golconda region in India and the weight is about 34.65 carat. According to Christie's it was discovered around 300 years ago. Nizam of Hyderabad was one of its owners who was described as the richest man in the world by TIME magazine in 1937. The current owner of the diamond is remained mysterious.

The Orange:

This is the largest fancy vivid orange diamond to have ever sold at an auction. Christie's Geneva Magnificent jewels sold the diamond for 35.5 million USD in November 2013. The diamond is 14.82 carat weight, pear-shaped stone which was discovered in South Africa and was owned by Bolivian industrialists famously known as "The Andean Rockefeller". The diamond created the record for the price per carat for any coloured diamond sold at auction of about 23,98,151 USD per carat.

The Eternal Pink:

The Eternal Pink is a rough diamond weighing 23.78 carat mined by De Beers at the Damtshaa mine in Botswana. It was made in to 10.57 carat cushion cut internally flawless fancy vivid purplish pink diamond. It was termed as "The most vivid pink diamond ever to come to market" in the auction.

This diamond was exhibited in many cities such as Dubai, Singapore, Hong Kong and Geneva. It was sold for 34.8 million USD in June 2023 auction held in New York.

The Zoe Diamond:

Paul Mellon sold The Zoe Diamond in Sotheby's New York auction for 32.6 million USD in November 2014. A private collector from Hong Kong purchased this diamond. The 9.75 carat fancy vivid blue diamond fetched more than twice its high estimate of 15 million USD. At the time of sale, the diamond set the world record for the most expensive blue diamond ever sold in the auction. Additionally, it created another record of the costliest price-per-carat for any diamond sold at auction at more than 3.3 million USD per carat.

Connection between Planets and Diamonds:

In ancient astrology Nine Planets are associated with various types of nine gems stones. In brief

- Sun-Ruby
- Moon-Pearl
- Mars-Coral
- Mercury-Emerald
- Jupiter-Topaz or Yellow Sapphire
- Venus-Diamond
- Saturn-Blue Sapphire
- Ragu-Garnet
- Kethu-Cat's Eye

Apart from these nine gemstones many other stones are generally used by the people and that was mentioned as Semi - Precious stones.

Conclusion:

The formation of Diamonds, the meaning behind the name, basic characteristics of the diamond, mining and the refining process, cutting procedures, appearance, quality, clarity, precious value of the diamond are all detailly explained in this article. Therefore, from this detail study we come to know that diamond have the history of about 2500 years.

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